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ENVIRONMENTAL CONSEQUENCES OF MILITARY ACTIONS

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Annotation: The main mechanisms and scales of environmental pollution due to military conflicts, as well as the further impact on the livelihoods of the population, have been studied and analyzed. In the course of the study, it was revealed that the most severe consequences of military operations are poisoning of soil, water and air.

Keywords: population, vital activity, environmental pollution

ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ПОСЛЕДСТВИЯ ВОЕННЫХ ДЕЙСТВИЙ

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Аннотация: Изучены и проанализированы основные механизмы и масштабы загрязнения окружающей среды вследствие

военных конфликтов, а также дальнейшее воздействие на жизнедеятельность населения. В процессе исследования выявлено, что наиболее тяжелыми последствиями военных действий являются отравление почвы, воды и воздуха.

Ключевые слова: население, жизнедеятельность, загрязнение окружающей среды

Relevance. The XII century is the century of high-tech industries, high technologies, great scientific discoveries, but the modern world is increasingly facing a number of global problems that affect the life of not only a certain state, but also of all mankind.

Military actions make a great contribution to the damage to nature. The most frequent type of military conflicts are regional and local wars and armed conflicts. At the same time, the political and economic consequences of this problem have been studied quite well, while the environmental ones have been studied to a lesser extent.

From the beginning of 1990 to the end of 1999, 118 armed conflicts took place in the world, in which 80 countries participated, in 2000-2011 – about 50. For the history of mankind, wars are not nonsense at all: for 5,500 years of the history of the world community, there were only a few periods of a short stretch of quiet life, but 100 years ago society did not possess weapons of mass destruction. At the moment, according to the available IAEA data, 10 countries have nuclear weapons and in cases of military conflict they can be used [1-3].

Goal. To study and analyze the main mechanisms and the extent of environmental pollution due to military conflicts, as well as the further impact on the livelihoods of the population.

Materials and methods of research. To achieve the purpose of this study, general scientific (analysis of the literature on the research problem, generalization, comparison and systematization of theoretical data) and descriptive (observation, interpretation, comparison) methods, as well as comparative-evaluative and analytical methods were used.

Results and their discussion. The environmental consequences of military-industrial activities are the production activities of enterprises of the military-industrial complex; testing of weapons systems in the production process; industrial and transport accidents. It is impossible not

to recall the tests of atomic weapons in the early 1960s, which led to a steady radioactive contamination of the planet's surface. According to the calculations of Academician A.D. Sakharov, this test caused the death from cancer from 4 to 5 million inhabitants of the planet. Their consequences will affect the health of many generations.

Dangers that can lead to mass death of people, loss of their health and livelihood, habitat disturbance, significant material damage. The main ones are: dangers that manifest themselves in the direct impact of the means of destruction on the human body. They lead to traumatic, radiation and chemical damage, as well as infectious diseases. In the future, defeats caused by the use of new types of weapons may be added to them. Hazards associated with the impact on people of secondary damage factors resulting from the destruction of radiation, chemical, biological, fire or explosive objects; hazards caused by the violation of the human habitat itself, the deprivation of his habitual and necessary life goods and services [1].

The most severe consequences are left by poisoning of the soil, water and air. The causes of pollution are usually:

- military equipment, since fighters, tanks, combat vessels have a pronounced ecological footprint: unlike civilian ones, there are no standards for their exhaust content, and when equipment is flooded in seas, rivers, swamps, fuel and oil spill, forming oil spots;
- explosives, ammunition (after their use, chemicals fall into the soil);
- toxic substances used by the warring parties (poisonous gases and herbicides settle in the soil and are not excreted for a long time).

Plants are sensitive to changes in the ecosystem. In the territories where toxic substances were released, some types of grasses, flowers, and shrubs may disappear. This contributes to the reduction of the number of rare, red-book plants. Trees often suffer during the fighting: they die from explosions, shells; they are destroyed when clearing territories and building fortifications and crossings. Fires, which always accompany wars, can destroy hundreds of hectares of forest.

There are known episodes of military operations when the war was literally waged against plants: for example, herbicides and defoliants (chemicals that kill plants and cause them to shed leaves) were used in Vietnam to deprive the rebels of shelters and a food source. During the

Second World War, the Nazis used "scorched earth tactics": grassroots fires over a large area that destroyed all living things in their path.

Animals also fully feel the horrors of war. Thousands of living beings are dying in the territories where there are fighting.

Huge damage is caused to the inhabitants of reservoirs (hydrobionts) when hit by projectiles: the blast wave stuns and kills thousands of fish, amphibians, snakes and aquatic mammals, and toxic substances that enter the environment by tons (traces of explosives, gases, petroleum products) cause the death of animals or mutations in subsequent generations.

In addition to direct damage, there is also indirect damage. War always leaves severe economic consequences that affect the relationship between man and nature. During the war and in the post-war years, when the economy is being restored, people often use natural resources in a predatory, irrational way. This includes logging without planting, open-pit mining, and water pollution by industrial effluents. In addition, during the war, funding for environmental projects is reduced: specially protected areas; forest restoration programs; environmental control of emissions. For example, during the Great Patriotic War, many nature reserves were left without means of subsistence, and only the heroism of workers and the help of caring people helped to preserve rare animals and plants [2-5].

In 1983, two floating oil wells were damaged during the war between Iran and Iraq. As a result, the Persian Gulf was turned into a sewer for a long time, where 1,100 tons of oil were poured daily.

One of the most terrible ways invented by mankind to destroy their own kind is nuclear weapons. Even his trial carries a mortal danger to humanity.

There are various methods of protecting the population from the effects of the consequences of hostilities. The protection of food, food raw materials, and water sources from possible contamination with radioactive, toxic (highly toxic) substances is directly related to the protection of the population. Protection of water sources is achieved by carrying out various engineering, technical and sanitary measures aimed at isolating water sources and observing the rules for using them. To protect farm animals from radioactive and toxic (highly toxic) substances, livestock premises are sealed, and if there is a shortage of them, other

premises are adapted and special shelters are built. Sanitary and hygienic measures include the organization and implementation of control over accommodation, nutrition, as well as educational work among the population about the need for strict compliance with sanitary and hygienic rules; conducting radiation, chemical and biological reconnaissance, dosimetric and chemical control [4, 6].

Military actions deal a huge blow to the ecological component of our planet. Based on statistical data, the following results were obtained: the Vietnam War with herbicides and defoliants destroyed vegetation on 360 thousand hectares of cultivated land, more than 40% of the acreage was affected. Of the 150 bird species, only 18 have been preserved, amphibians and insects have been almost completely destroyed, and many fish species in rivers.

Iraq's war against Kuwait in 1990-1991 also brought severe environmental consequences. After the war, there were lakes of oil, places of extinguished fires, bird corpses on the coast and yellowed mango thickets. Scientists note that the clouds of smoke and soot that swept over the southern regions of Asia may have affected the rainy seasons and significantly reduced harvests. The latter circumstance is a sign of ecological warfare [1, 5].

Military conflicts lead to a decrease in the number of people in a particular region, which cannot but affect the environment. During the Chechen conflict of 1995-1997, the local population was halved (due to migration movements and the number of victims).

According to the UN, only 44 years after the end of World War II, 1,880 nuclear weapons tests took place on earth. In total, the power of the test explosions carried out by the United States alone is 11050 times greater than the power of the bomb dropped on Hiroshima at one time. All these years there has been a continuous accumulation of radionuclides in the environment, and radioactive radiation on the surface of the planet had already reached 2% of the natural background by 1963.

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